

IPBES AR BBA Chapter 2 – Snowball literature search for literature on business dependency on biodiversity (R4)

Crops with their corresponding ISIC subcategories¹

Crop	ISIC subcategory	Crop	ISIC subcategory
Lemon	Citrus	Coconut	oleaginous
Orange	Citrus	Oil_palm	oleaginous
Tangerine	Citrus	Olive	oleaginous
Barley	Cereal	Clover	other_non-perennial
Grain maize	Cereal	Rubber tree	other perennial
Millet	Cereal	Cardamom	perennial_non-perennial
Oat	Cereal	Chilies	perennial_non-perennial
Rye	Cereal	Cinnamon	perennial_non-perennial
Sorghum	Cereal	Clove	perennial_non-perennial
Wheat	Cereal	Ginger	perennial_non-perennial
Beans	Legumes	Nutmeg	perennial_non-perennial
Broad_beans	Legumes	Vanilla	perennial_non-perennial
Chick_peas	Legumes	White_pepper	perennial_non-perennial
Cow_peas	Legumes	Apple	pome_stone_fruits
Lentils	Legumes	Cherry	pome_stone_fruits
Lupins	Legumes	Peach	pome_stone_fruits
Peas	Legumes	Pear	pome_stone_fruits
Pegeon_pea	Legumes	pome_stone_fruits	pome_stone_fruits
Blueberries	Berries	Quince	pome_stone_fruits

¹ <https://siccode.com/isic-code-hierarchy/a/agriculture-forestry-fishing>

Crop	ISIC subcategory
Currant	Berries
Gooseberries	Berries
Raspberry	Berries
Strawberries	Berries
Kiwi	Berries
Cocoa	Beverage
Coffee	Beverage
Mate	Beverage
Tea	Beverage
Almond	Nuts
Brazil_nut	Nuts
Cashew	Nuts
Chestnut	Nuts
Hazelnut	Nuts
Macadamia	Nuts
Pistachios	Nuts
Walnut	Nuts
Cotton	Fibres
Jute	Fibres
Sisal	Fibres
Cantaloupe	fruit_veg
Cucumber	fruit_veg
Eggplant	fruit_veg
Tomato	fruit_veg

Crop	ISIC subcategory
Rice	rice
Carrot	root_bulb_tuberous
Cassava	root_bulb_tuberous
Garlic	root_bulb_tuberous
Leeks	root_bulb_tuberous
Onion	root_bulb_tuberous
Potato	root_bulb_tuberous
Sweet_potato	root_bulb_tuberous
Turnips	root_bulb_tuberous
Yam	root_bulb_tuberous
Sugarcane	sucargane
Tobacco	Tobacco
Dates	tropical_subtropical_fruits
Fig	tropical_subtropical_fruits
Mango	tropical_subtropical_fruits
Papaya	tropical_subtropical_fruits
Passionfruit	tropical_subtropical_fruits
Pineapple	tropical_subtropical_fruits
Pomegranate	tropical_subtropical_fruits
Soursop	tropical_subtropical_fruits
Castor_bean	oil_seeds
Groundnut	oil_seeds
Linseed	oil_seeds
Mustard_seed	oil_seeds

Crop	ISIC subcategory
Watermelon	fruit_veg
Grapes	Grapes
Cabbage	leafy_stem_veg
Cauliflower	leafy_stem_veg
Lettuce	leafy_stem_veg
Spinach	leafy_stem_veg

Crop	ISIC subcategory
Niger_seed	oil_seeds
Rapeseed	oil_seeds
Safflower_seed	oil_seeds
Sesame_seed	oil_seeds
Soybean_soja	oil_seeds
Sunflower	oil_seeds
Corn	grain_mil_products